

CREATING LEVERAGE TO ENHANCE BIODIVERSITY OUTCOMES
OF GLOBAL BIOMASS TRADE

Map of public and private policies and governance mechanisms

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About CLEVER

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report maps key public and private policies and governance mechanisms regulating legal and sustainable forest and ecosystem-risk biomass value chains across demand and supply-side countries and regions. Based on a qualitative data analysis of policy and legislative documents and a review of the academic literature, we first developed a comprehensive Excel database of key forest and ecosystem-related policy and governance types. Second, we developed a categorization of six different policy and governance types constructed along the degree of compulsion (legally binding and non-legally binding) and direct participation of actors (main actors: state, main actors: nonstate, and joint participation of state and nonstate actors) at three geographic levels (international, transnational, and (sub-)national). We defined the types, theoretically drawing on regulatory governance literature, and provided key illustrative examples.

INTRODUCTION

Over the last three decades, numerous global environmental agreements, transnational nonstate market governance mechanisms, and state-sanctioned regulations have been developed to tackle deforestation, forest degradation, biodiversity loss, and climate change (Begemann et al., 2021; Sotirov et al., 2020). Nevertheless, the increasingly strong demand for forestry (e.g., timber, pulp, paper) and agricultural (e.g., cattle, oil palm, soya) forest and ecosystem-risk commodities (FERCs) continues to cause deforestation, ecosystem degradation, and biodiversity loss, particularly in the tropics and subtropics (Pendrill et al., 2019a, 2019b). FERCs are needed for food (e.g., food and beverage products) and non-food (e.g., soy for animal feed, oil palm for cosmetics, wood products for biofuel, and packaging) value chains. These compounding demands increase land use pressure and competition, adding to the governance complexity of sustainable land use, trade, and consumption (Bamière & Bellassen, 2018; Gaba, 2018). Timber logging is the most important driver of global forest degradation (Hosonuma et al., 2012) and an important precursor to deforestation (Vancutsem et al., 2021). Agriculture is the most important driver of global deforestation, driving 90%–99% of tropical deforestation (Pendrill et al., 2022).

In addition to environmental sustainability issues such as biodiversity loss and climate change, deforestation, and forest degradation are associated with severe human rights violations (Global Witness, 2022; Human Rights Watch, 2019). Furthermore, forests worldwide are crucial for providing income and livelihoods to rural communities and indigenous peoples (FAO & UNEP, 2020). These telecoupled challenges connect demand- and supply-side regions through global FERC value chains characterized by "complex forms of mutual interdependencies across distant regions" (Lenschow et al., 2016, p. 152). In the absence of a legally binding global agreement that can justify and impose sustainability or legality standards for FERC production in both demand and supply-side countries (Cashore & Stone, 2014; Dimitrov, 2005), numerous transnational and (sub-)national policy and institutional efforts seek to ensure the conservation, sustainable use, and restoration of forests and ecosystems (Sotirov et al., 2020).

This report maps and classifies key public and private policies and governance mechanisms regulating legal and/or sustainable forest and ecosystem-risk biomass supply chains across demand and supply-side countries and regions to contribute to closing knowledge gaps concerning the policy (in)coherence of the different initiatives at different geographic scales.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Building on global environmental governance, international relations, and Europeanization scholarship, we conceptualize different types of forest and ecosystem-related policy and governance mechanisms.

First, we distinguish between the degree of compulsion (legally binding and non-legally binding) and direct participation of actors (main actors: state, main actors: nonstate, and joint participation of state and nonstate actors)(e.g., Sotirov et al., 2020).

Legally binding refers to legally binding public or private law (i.e., hard law). Public law regulates the relationship between governmental actors (e.g., public authorities) and private actors (e.g., individuals, NGOs, corporate actors), and other governmental actors (e.g., EU and tropical producer country governments). Private law regulates relationships between private actors through contractual agreements and other private laws (e.g., property law). Compliance can be enforced through sanctions and penalties (e.g., in administrative or criminal courts). Unlike under legally binding initiatives, (non)compliance under non-legally binding initiatives (i.e., soft law) cannot be enforced through legal procedures imposing penalties and sanctions (e.g., Abbott et al., 2021, Cashore, 2002).

State actors include governmental authorities (e.g., EU institutions, competent authorities, and ministries in non-EU countries). Nonstate actors include environmental Nongovernmental Organizations (NGOs), Civil Society Organizations (CSOs), corporate actors, and certifiers. We separate between the direct participation of actors by distinguishing whether state or nonstate actors are the main actors initiating, designing, implementing, and enforcing policies and governance mechanisms. Additionally, state and nonstate actors can jointly be involved in initiating, designing, implementing, and enforcing policies and governance mechanisms (e.g., Abbott et al., 2021).

Second, we distinguish between policy and governance types at three geographic levels – international, transnational, and (sub-)national. We understand "international" forest and ecosystem-related policy and governance initiatives among any type of actors that exclusively concern global issues and are agreed upon by a global range of actors (e.g., Chester & Moomaw, 2008; Sotirov et al., 2020). We understand "transnational" as being narrower in geopolitical terms, including interactions across and beyond national borders and between any type of actors. While transnational initiatives also have an international reach, their reach is narrower in that they are not agreed upon by a global range of actors. We include in this category national laws that have an extraterritorial reach. Furthermore, we understand supranational initiatives as having a transnational reach. "Supranational" refers to ceding decision-making authority to an organization or body that exists above the national level for a

group of national members. This network of national regulators assists in translating rules to national contexts (Abbott et al., 2021). In the European Union, a prominent example of a supranational body, EU Member States delegate certain executive, legislative, and judicial powers to supranational institutions such as the European Commission, European Parliament, Council of the EU, and European Court of Justice, empowering them with authority in public policymaking (Hix & Høyland, 2011). Multilateral refers to agreements between three or more actors, and bilateral refers to agreements between two actors (e.g., Sotirov et al., 2020). "National" refers to forest and ecosystem-related policy and governance initiatives among any type of actors that are set at the national level and apply within a country's jurisdiction. This includes initiatives at the subnational (i.e., local) level (Hix & Høyland, 2011; Keohane & Nye, 2000).

OBJECTIVES

This report aims to map and classify key public and private policies and governance mechanisms regulating legal and/or sustainable forest and ecosystem-risk biomass supply chains across demand and supply-side countries and regions. This mapping follows a matrix describing different types of policy and governance mechanisms concerning three variables (degree of compulsion, direct participation of actors, and geographical scope), and provides the basis for the contextual understanding of this regulatory landscape, on which further CLEVER work focused on the design and implementation of selected policies and governance mechanisms will build.

METHODS

Mapping results are based on a comprehensive literature review of the state-of-the-art research, grey literature, and policy and legislative documents. The authors identified key public and private policies and governance mechanisms based on their respective expertise.

We first developed a comprehensive Excel database of key international forest and ecosystem-related policy and governance types (Berning et al., 2023). This database includes the geographical scope (i.e., international, transnational, and (sub-)national) and country-specific and regional geographical scope information. The main geographical focus areas for identifying relevant policy and governance mechanisms were the EU (as a major consumer and trader of FERCs), and Brazil, Cameroon, and Gabon (as key FERC producers). Furthermore, the research teams expanded the database to additional geographical regions based on related ongoing research on demand- and supply-side timber legality policies in key producer and consumer countries (e.g., USA, Australia, Indonesia, India).

Beyond the name and abbreviation of the respective policies and governance mechanisms, we included key information about the timeframe. The "year of initiation" refers to 1) the year when a legally binding initiative that is not formally adopted yet has been initiated or 2) the year of initiating a non-legally binding initiative if no official adoption year has been communicated. The "year of adoption" refers to 1) the year when a legally binding or non-legally binding initiative gets formally adopted by decision-makers or 2) the year when a non-legally binding initiative has been formally established, for instance, by announcing its official foundation. This is followed with information about when legally binding instruments entered into force. The "year of entry into force" exclusively relates to legally binding initiatives and refers to the year when an initiative becomes legally binding for the first time. The "years of partial applications or amendments" refers to 1) the years when a legally binding policy applies partially after having entered into force or 2) the years a legally binding or non-binding initiative got amended. The "year of expiration" refers to the year a legally binding or non-legally binding initiative expires, for instance, through a sunset clause in a regulation or a preset time frame. For EU-partner country Forest Law Enforcement Governance and Trade (FLEGT) Voluntary Partnership Agreements (VPAs), the year of initiation refers to the year of signing a VPA with the EU. The year of adoption refers to the year of ratifying the VPA with the EU. The "year of entry into force" category refers to the year of entry into force following the publication of the VPA in the Official Journal of the European Union. The "year of partial applications or amendments" refers to the start of FLEGT licensing.

Second, we developed a categorization of the different policy and governance types by drawing on Sotirov et al.'s (2020) classification of six international forest policy and governance types. This includes 1) multilateral treaty regimes (international hard

law), 2) non-binding multilateral agreements (international soft law), 3) transnational regulatory governance (hybrid regimes), 4) transnational public-private partnerships (collaborative institutions), 5) transnational nonstate market-driven governance (private regulation), and 6) transnational private sector partnerships (industry self-regulation). We expanded this classification by distinguishing between the three geographic levels – international, transnational, and (sub-)national – to analyze the (in-)coherence of policies and governance mechanisms regulating FERC supply chains across supply- and demand-side jurisdictions (cf. Chester & Moomaw, 2008; Lenschow et al., 2016).

RESULTS

We identified six policy and governance types constructed along the degree of compulsion (legally binding vs. non-legally binding) and direct participation of actors (main actors: state, main actors: nonstate, and joint participation of state and nonstate actors) at the international, transnational, and (sub-)national levels. The following sections expand on the overarching goals of the respective policy and governance types, followed by a description of how the instruments work and some key examples from our database (Berning et al., 2023). Table 1 provides an overview of our classification of key public and private policies and governance mechanisms regulating legal and sustainable forest and ecosystem-risk biomass supply chains across demand and supply-side jurisdictions. Tables 2 - 4 outline key examples.

Table 1: Overview of policies and governance types regulating legal and/or sustainable forest and ecosystem-risk biomass supply chains (types I - VI).

	Legally binding	Non-legally binding
Main actors: state actors	TYPE I: a) International b) Transnational c) (Sub-)national	TYPE II: a) International b) Transnational c) (Sub-)national
State and nonstate actors	TYPE III: a) International b) Transnational c) (Sub-)national	TYPE IV: a) International b) Transnational c) (Sub-)national
Main actors: nonstate actors	TYPE V a) International b) Transnational c) (Sub-)national	TYPE VI a) International b) Transnational c) (Sub-)national

Table 2: International policies and governance mechanisms (a).

	Legally binding	Non-legally binding
Main actors: state actors	<p>TYPE I a International hard law:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Global Forest Convention (failed), International Tropical Timber Agreement (ITTA), Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD), Convention on International Trade in Endangered Species of Wild Fauna and Flora (CITES), United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC) and its agreements including the Kyoto Protocol, and the Paris Agreement, World Trade Organization (WTO) Agreement, General Agreement on Tariffs and Trade (GATT) 1994 and associated agreements 	<p>TYPE II a International soft law:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The 1972 Stockholm Declaration, the 1987 Sustainable Development Brundtland Report, the United Nations Conference on Environment and Development (UNCED), the United Nations Millennium Declaration (and its Millennium Development Goals (MDGs)), the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development (and its Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)), the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework (GBF), The International Arrangement on Forests (IAF), United Nations Forum on Forests (UNFF), the UNFF Secretariat, the UNFF Global Forest Financing Facilitation Network (GFFFN), the UNFF Trust Fund, the UN Strategic Plan for Forests (UNSPF), the UN Forest Instrument, and the Warsaw Framework for REDD+ (reducing emissions from deforestation and forest degradation in developing countries, and additional forest-related activities that protect the climate)
State and nonstate actors	<p>TYPE III a NA</p>	<p>TYPE IV a</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN)
Main actors: nonstate actors	<p>TYPE V a: NA</p>	<p>TYPE VI a: NA</p>

Table 3: Transnational policies and governance mechanisms (b).

Type	Legally binding	Non-legally binding
Main actors: state actors	<p>TYPE I b</p> <p>Transnational public regulation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> US Lacey Act and its 2008 amendment <p>Transnational free trade agreement:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> EU-MERCOSUR free trade agreement with TSD chapter <p>Supranational public regulation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Certain EU laws (e.g., EU's Habitats Directive and the Birds Directive, EU's Regulation on land use and forestry (LULUCF), EU Climate Law, EU Nature Restoration Law [forthcoming], Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) Regulations) MERCOSUR's Framework Agreement on the Environment Amazon Cooperation Treaty Organization (ACTO) and its declarations 	<p>TYPE II b</p> <p>Transnational public-public partnerships:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Amsterdam Declaration Partnership, Forest, Agriculture and Commodity Trade (FACT) Dialogue (COP26), EU-partner country Forest Partnerships, EU-China Bilateral Coordination Mechanism, and (former) EU support for Myanmar <p>Supranational strategies & initiatives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> EU strategies and initiatives (e.g., EU Farm to Fork Strategy, EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030, EU Forest Strategy for 2030, European Green Deal, EU FLEGT Action Plan, EU Action Plan Against Wildlife Trafficking) Central African Economic and Monetary Community countries' decision to ban the export of raw logs African Union's Agenda 2063 ASEAN'S ASCC (ASEAN Socio-Cultural Community) Blueprint 2025 Belém Declaration
State and nonstate actors	<p>TYPE III b</p> <p>Transnational hybrid regulation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> EU Timber Regulation (EUTR), The UK's Timber and Timber Products Placing on the Market Regulations (UKTR), Australia's Illegal Logging Prohibition Act (ILPA), Japanese Clean Wood Act (CWA), Swiss Timber Trade Ordinance, The South Korean Act on Sustainable Use of Timbers, EU Regulation on Deforestation-free products (EUDR), Renewable Energy Directive (RED), EU Regulation to prevent, deter and eliminate illegal, unreported and unregulated fishing (IUU), UK Environment Act 2021 and specifically its due diligence provisions on forest risk commodities <p>Transnational hybrid free trade agreement</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> EU and UK-partner country FLEGT VPAs & EU and UK FLEGT 	<p>TYPE IV b:</p> <p>Transnational public-private partnerships:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The Conscious Food Systems Alliance (CoFSA), UN Global Compact, Bonn Challenge, Collaborative Partnership on Forests (CPF), The Tropical Forest Alliance, the Lowering Emissions by Accelerating Forest finance (LEAF) Coalition, New York Declaration on Forests

Type	Legally binding	Non-legally binding
	Regulation	
Main actors: nonstate actors	<p>TYPE V b: Transnational private regulation</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • NGO-led certification: e.g., Rainforest Alliance • Industry-led certification: e.g., Programme for the Endorsement of Forest Certification (PEFC), 4C certification • Multi-stakeholder-led certification: e.g., Forest Stewardship Council (FSC), International Sustainability & Carbon Certification (ISCC), Roundtable on Sustainable Palm Oil (RSPO), Round Table on Responsible Soy (RTRS) 	<p>TYPE VI b: Transnational industry self-regulation</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Voluntary commitments: e.g., zero deforestation pledges from multinational companies such as Nestlé and Unilever • Codes of conduct: e.g., responsible sourcing practices, transparency initiatives • Corporate Social Responsibility initiatives: e.g., financial and capacity-building support to smallholders, such as Mondelez International's Cocoa Life initiative in Brazil • Corporate coalitions: e.g., Consumer Goods Forum Forest Positive Coalition, Soy Transparency Coalition, Retail Soy Group, Global Roundtable for Sustainable Beef (GRSB)

Table 4: (Sub-)national policies and governance mechanisms (c).

Type	Legally binding	Non-legally binding
Main actors: state actors	<p>TYPE I c: (Sub-)national public regulation</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Public laws: Brazil Forest Code-Law 12.651/2012, Cameroon Law 94/01, 1994 (regulations for forestry, wildlife, and fisheries), Gabon Forest Code- Law 016/01, 2001 • Public certification: Indonesian National Timber Legality Assurance System (TLAS), mandatory FSC certification in Gabon (not legally binding yet but planned to become so), Malaysian Sustainable Palm Oil (MSPO) Certification, Indonesian Palm Oil Council (ISPO) 	<p>TYPE II c: (Sub-)national strategies & initiatives</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Brazil National Climate Change Adaptation Plan, Cameroon National Strategy for Reducing Emissions from Deforestation and Forest Degradation, etc., Gabon National Biodiversity Strategy and Action Plan
State and nonstate actors	<p>TYPE III c: NA</p>	<p>TYPE IV c: NA</p>
Main actors: nonstate actors	<p>TYPE V c: (Sub-)national private regulation</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • G4 cattle agreement, Brazilian Soy Moratorium 	<p>TYPE VI c: (Sub-)national industry self-regulation</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Voluntary commitments (e.g., Brazilian's biggest retailer group "Grupo Pão de Açúcar" 's zero deforestation pledge and signing the Cerrado Manifesto), • Codes of conduct (e.g., responsible sourcing practices, transparency initiatives) • Corporate Social Responsibility initiatives (e.g., financial and capacity-building support to smallholders).

Type I: State actors, legally binding

Policies and governance mechanisms under type I mostly involve state actors, are legally binding, and exist at the international, transnational, and (sub-)national levels.

Type I a: International level

Examples at the international level include **multilateral treaty regimes (i.e., international hard law)**. The overall goal of multilateral treaties is to establish agreed social, environmental, and economic standards between signing member states under international law. As international legal documents, treaties set binding legal commitments and obligations on state parties. These commitments and obligations often serve as a basis for national and transnational policy and governance mechanisms. Multilateral treaties are formal, legally binding written agreements between actors under international law, to which usually a global range of sovereign states are parties. They are considered legally binding by the International Court of Justice, the United Nations (UN), and the international community because these conventions and agreements have undergone a process of negotiation, signature, and ratification by member states. Nonetheless, if the treaty is not institutionalized in domestic law, it will not be legally binding since the UN has no power of coercion to enforce compliance (Pauwelyn, 2003). The obligation on the member state is legally binding once the treaty is ratified. However, if it is not implemented through national law and policies, the state may not be compliant with its international obligations.

Bodies established in the treaty, often international organizations such as UN agencies, provide and organize implementation or dispute mechanisms to support accountability and compliance with certain multilateral treaties. An example is how the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC) Secretariat provides a transparency and accountability framework for state parties (UNFCCC Enhanced Transparency Framework) and nonstate members (UNFCCC Secretariat Recognition and Accountability Framework for non-Party stakeholder climate action) to monitor and review the accomplishment of the Paris Agreement. Furthermore, the Secretariat also organizes the annual Conference of Parties, providing a space for negotiation and exchange (UNFCCC, n.d.; UNFCCC, 2023).

Multilateral treaty regimes are characterized by the involvement of sovereign state actors who become parties to the treaty, as in negotiating, signing, implementing, and enforcing the respective treaties. Nonstate actors (e.g., NGOs & CSOs) frequently influence the agenda-setting and initiative/instrument design and serve a watchdog function. They can support the implementation and monitoring, and influence the enforcement of treaty compliance (e.g., by providing data and whistle-blowing of states' noncompliance). An example of nonstate actor participation in the climate regime is the Nonstate Actor Zone for Climate Action (NAZCA) initiative coordinated by UNFCCC (Hickmann et al., 2021).

Specific forest-related examples of policies and governance mechanisms under this type include the failed Global Forest Convention and the International Tropical Timber Agreement (ITTA). Biodiversity-related Conventions include the Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD) and the Convention on International Trade in Endangered Species (CITES). Climate-related multilateral treaties include the UNFCCC and its agreements, including the Kyoto Protocol and the Paris Agreement (Berning et al., 2022; 2023; Conca & Dabelko, 2018; Sotirov et al., 2020; Abbott, 2012; Abbott & Snidal, 2021). Trade-related examples include the World Trade Organization (WTO) Agreement, General Agreement on Tariffs and Trade (GATT) 1994, and associated agreements to reduce trade barriers and apply nondiscriminatory rules (e.g., Weinstein & Charnovitz, 2001).

Type I b: Transnational level

Examples at the transnational level include transnational public regulation, transnational free trade agreements, and supranational public regulation. **Transnational public regulation** aims to institutionalize social, environmental, and economic standards that transcend national borders through legally binding public hard laws with command and control rules (e.g., due care requirements). Transnational public regulations are enacted by individual states or through a formally established body representing the states, whereby the states have ceded some of their national sovereignty to the body. Noncompliance can be sanctioned with penalties (e.g., financial penalties, imprisonment). Unlike transnational hybrid regulation (see type III b), transnational public regulation mostly involves state actors in regulatory implementation and enforcement processes. Nonstate actors (e.g., NGOs, corporate actors) can have an influential role during the regulatory agenda setting and design. An example from the forest sector is the US Lacey Act with its 2008 amendment, requesting economic actors to exercise due care along supply chains (e.g., Leipold et al., 2016).

Transnational free trade agreements aim to establish bilaterally or multilaterally agreed trade rules which can include economic, social, and environmental standards. While the main goal of free trade agreements is inherently trade-related, they are frequently combined with legally binding or voluntary commitments to respect socio-economic (e.g., human rights, land use rights, employment rights) and environmental standards (e.g., climate, biodiversity, deforestation) in the form of Trade and Sustainable Development Chapters (TSDs) (Dür et al., 2020; Keohane, 2002; Weinstein & Charnovitz, 2001; Yildirim et al., 2020). Similar to international hard laws (see type I a), transnational free trade agreements are initially voluntary and become legally binding to all involved parties upon ratification by all signatories. They are enacted by individual states or through a formally established body representing the states, whereby the states have ceded some of their national sovereignty to the body (usually a regional body). (E)NGOs and CSOs can have an influential role during the design (e.g., inclusion of socio-environmental standards) and implementation phase

(e.g., monitoring and enforcement). Corporate actors also influence the agenda-setting and design (e.g., achieve tariff reductions, secure market access) and implementation phase (e.g., (non-)compliance)). Examples in the agricultural sector include the currently negotiated EU-MERCOSUR trade agreement with a TSD chapter between the EU and the Mercosur countries Argentina, Brazil, Paraguay, and Uruguay (Berning et al., 2022; Berning & Sotirov, 2023; Sotirov et al., 2022).

Supranational public regulation aims to coherently regulate relevant public policy at a scale encompassing multiple states, possibly in a region (Gruber, 2000; Hix & Høyland, 2011). These policies are legally binding and are set by a supranational body (Gruber, 2000). They are designed to be implemented and enforced at a national level in the countries that are members of the body, either directly after adoption by the supranational body or through adoption into national legal frameworks (Gruber, 2000; Hix & Høyland, 2011). State actors enact supranational public policies through a formally established body representing the states, whereby the states have ceded some of their national sovereignty to the body (Gruber, 2000). To a lesser extent, however, nonstate actors, like NGOs, can also play a role. This can occur during the design phase (e.g., through advocacy) or the implementation phase (e.g., through monitoring and enforcement support). Corporate actors can also influence the design of public policies (e.g., through lobbying activities) and implementation (e.g., (non-)compliance)).

Relevant examples from the area of biodiversity conservation include the EU's Habitats Directive and the Birds Directive, which require the designation of areas for the conservation of flora and fauna (e.g., through the Natura 2000 network) (Evans, 2006). Another example from the land use and forestry sector is the EU's Regulation on land use and forestry (LULUCF), defining how these sectors should contribute to the EU's climate goals. Additional examples include the EU's Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) Regulations, the EU Climate Law, and the forthcoming EU Nature Restoration Law. The EU Timber Regulation (EUTR) and EU Regulation on Deforestation-free products (EUDR) also apply to the EU and its Member States. However, they have a more transnational character as they seek to regulate production practices outside the EU through demand-side import legislation, as well as regulating domestic trade (i.e., prohibitions and due diligence requirements) (see type III b) (Berning et al., 2023; Berning & Sotirov, 2023; Sotirov et al., 2021). Examples outside of the EU include the MERCOSUR Framework Agreement on the Environment and the Amazon Cooperation Treaty Organization (ACTO) and its declarations.

Type I c: (Sub-)national level

Examples at the (sub-)national level include public laws and public certification schemes. **National public laws** regulate biodiversity and biomass-related issues in a national or sub-national state jurisdiction. They are a key mechanism for states to

regulate relevant matters at the domestic level (Kelsen, 1949). These are legally binding as they are part of the domestic legal framework by the state (Kelsen, 1949).

The state is responsible for leading the initiation, design, implementation, monitoring, and enforcement through different formal state institutions and agencies. State actors at different domestic levels can also be involved if there are processes of governmental decentralization in place (Kelsen, 1949). Nonstate actors (e.g., NGOs) may participate in the agenda-setting of public policymaking, contribute to implementation and enforcement via a watchdog role, and be impacted by the regulation in place. Corporate actors can also influence the design of national public policies (e.g., through lobbying activities) and implementation (e.g., (non-)compliance)).

Essential examples in supplier countries include countries' forest and forestry-related regulations, such as in Brazil (Forest Code-Law 12.651/2012 on the protection of Native Forests), Cameroon (Law 94/01 of 20 January 1994 laying down regulations for forestry, wildlife, and fisheries) (Ekoko, 2000), and Gabon (Law 016/01 of December 31, 2001 establishing the Forest Code in the Gabonese Republic) (Berning et al., 2023; Yobo & Kasumi, 2016).

National public sustainability certification and legality verification schemes of forestry and agricultural products seek to establish national land use standards to facilitate trade with regulated consumer countries and regions. They seek to stimulate demand through increased transparency and trust in legal and socio-environmentally sustainable production practices. Unlike private regulatory initiatives such as NGO and industry certification schemes (type V b), they apply to the entire country to establish harmonized standards and avoid fragmentation (e.g., Partzsch, 2020; Wijaya & Glasbergen, 2016).

National public sustainability certification and legality verification schemes are not necessarily, but frequently, mandatory for corporate actors. As such, compliance is frequently a prerequisite for many corporate actors to engage in market activities (e.g., Partzsch, 2020; Wijaya & Glasbergen, 2016). Governments or public institutions are directly involved in or responsible for initiating, designing, implementing, and enforcing public sustainability certification and legality verification schemes. Additionally, nonstate actors such as (E)NGOs and CSOs are frequently involved in agenda-setting and co-design. Furthermore, they serve a watchdog function and support governments in the implementation and enforcement phases (e.g., assessment and certification of production processes, chains of custody, companies, commodities, and products). Corporate actors can also be involved in the design (e.g., through lobbying activities) and implementation (e.g., (non-)compliance)).

Key examples include Indonesia's National Timber Legality Assurance System (TLAS) called Sistem Verifikasi Legalitas Kayu (SVLK). SVLK is a government-run system based on an external third-party certification approach. It comprises two sets of standards:

a legality standard (VLK) for different types of processing industries and a sustainability standard (PHPL) for forest operations by private concessions and state companies (Maryudi et al., 2017; Savilaakso et al., 2017; Susilawati & Kanowski, 2020). The SVLK was recently renamed as Sistem Verifikasi Legalitas and Kelestarian to underline that the system is designed to foster forest sustainability in addition to legality (Berning et al., 2022). Cameroon has developed a national TLAS as part of the VPA process, but it is not operational for EU exports. Gabon has also developed its own legality verification scheme, called System of Control of Legality and Traceability (SCLT) (Berning et al., 2023). In addition, Gabon announced in 2018 that FSC certification will become mandatory for all forest concessions in the country. This decision is not yet legally binding but is planned to become so. In Southeast Asia, mandatory public certification schemes for palm oil [i.e., Indonesian Sustainable Palm Oil (ISPO), Malaysian Sustainable Palm Oil (MSPO)] emerged as alternatives to stricter private certification schemes (e.g., RSPO) (Partzsch, 2020; Wijaya & Glasbergen, 2016).

Type II: State actors, non-legally binding

Like type I, policies and governance mechanisms under type II mostly involve state actors and exist at the international, transnational, and (sub-)national levels. However, unlike type I, they are non-legally binding.

Type II a: International level

Examples at the international level include **non-binding multilateral agreements (i.e., international soft law)**. Similar to multilateral treaty regimes (see type I a), these agreements frequently relate to social, environmental, and economic principles to be held by countries. However, they are legally non-binding. Non-binding multilateral agreements have increased since the beginning of the 21st century and usually contain a degree of normative character and political weight. They may also provide the basis for facilitating consensus among states, which can, in the future, influence the development of internationally legally binding treaties. Despite their non-binding nature, these instruments have been used to establish political commitments and provide international guiding principles (Patrick, 2015; Wanner, 2021; Sotirov et al., 2020; Dimitrov, 2005; Abbott, 2012; Abbott & Snidal, 2021).

Similar to multilateral treaty regimes, multilateral agreements are usually negotiated by a global range of sovereign states. In international law, non-binding agreements contain political or moral commitments but are not intended to create legal rights and obligations (Abbott, 2012; Patrick, 2015; Abbott & Snidal, 2021). They cover a variety of instruments, including declarations, agreed international agendas, and goals.

Non-binding multilateral agreements may have the direct participation of all actors in society, depending on how open the participation process is. States are the main negotiating actors who ultimately decide on the agreed terms and conditions.

However, in the process of an agenda or declaration, other nonstate stakeholders (e.g., NGOs) may also be involved and influence the initiation and design of the final agreement. Nonstate actors frequently also play a role in monitoring and implementing these agreements (e.g., the Partnerships for Sustainable Development Goals platform to assist in implementing the 2030 Agenda) (Bull & McNeill, 2019). International organizations will organize and convene encounters to monitor, revise, and understand how principles are being applied in each national context. However, countries are not obliged to participate (e.g., the annual High Level Political Forum on Sustainable Development to review the 2030 Agenda) (Morin & Orsini, 2020).

Key non-binding UN conferences, agendas, and frameworks include the 1972 Stockholm Declaration, 1987 Sustainable Development Brundtland Report, 1992 UN Conference on Environment and Development (UNCED) in Rio (Agenda 21) and following 2002 Summit, 2000 Millennium Development Goals (MDGs), 2015 UN Agenda 2030 on Sustainable Development (Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)), and the recent Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework (GBF) (Morin & Orsini, 2020; Dimitrov, 2005; Abbott, 2012; Abbott & Snidal, 2021). Specific forest-related examples under this type include the International Arrangement on Forests (IAF), the UN Forum on Forests (UNFF), the UNFF Secretariat, the UNFF Global Forest Financing Facilitation Network (GFFFN), the UNFF Trust Fund, the UN Strategic Plan for Forests (UNSPF), the UN Forest Instrument, the concepts on Sustainable Forest Management (SFM) and Criteria and Indicators (C&I), and the Warsaw Framework for REDD+. REDD refers to "Reducing emissions from deforestation and forest degradation in developing countries". The "+" stands for additional forest-related activities that protect the climate (e.g., sustainable forest management and the conservation and enhancement of forest carbon stocks) (Berning et al., 2023; Sotirov et al., 2020).

Type II b: Transnational level

Examples at the transnational level include transnational public-public partnerships and supranational strategies and initiatives. The main goal of **transnational public-public partnerships** is to cooperate among public entities to jointly and more effectively address shared cross-national objectives by leveraging the diverse expertise, resources, and capabilities of involved partners. Transnational public-public partnerships are voluntary and can be organized in different forms, depending on the involved governmental entities and specific objectives. These cross-border partnerships between governments of different countries or regions are frequently formed around issues such as trade, deforestation, biodiversity loss, climate change, and socio-economic development. Government-to-government cooperation can take different forms and include dialogues, financial cooperation, the implementation of jointly planned action items, and knowledge-sharing activities such as information and expertise exchange to achieve shared goals and objectives. Unlike public-private partnerships (see type IV b), public-public partnerships exclusively involve public sector entities at the local, regional, and/or (sub-)national

levels. They may rely on nonstate actors (e.g., NGOs, CSOs, corporate actors) during the implementation of agreed action items (e.g., execution of programs).

Specific forest-related examples under this type include the Forest, Agriculture and Commodity Trade (FACT) Dialogue, launched by the UK as COP26 President with Indonesia as co-chair. The dialogue brings together the largest producers and consumers of internationally traded forest-risk agricultural commodities (e.g., palm oil, soya, cocoa, beef, and timber) to fight deforestation, biodiversity loss, and climate change while promoting sustainable trade and development. The Amsterdam Declaration Partnership is a strategic alliance between FERC import-dependent European countries committed to achieving zero-deforestation supply chains and includes nine signatory countries: Belgium, Denmark, France, Germany, Italy, the Netherlands, Norway, Spain, and the UK (Berning et al., 2023). A recent example includes the launch of EU-partner country Forest Partnerships (e.g., Memorandum of Understandings between the EU and Guyana, Mongolia, the Republic of Congo, Uganda, and Zambia). Other examples include bilateral cooperation mechanisms on timber legality, such as the EU-China Bilateral Coordination Mechanism and (former) EU support for Myanmar to improve its forest governance and prevent illegal logging.

Supranational strategies and initiatives have a similar goal as supranational public policies (see type I b). They aim to give coherent, strategic direction and guidance to biodiversity and biomass-trade governance or catalyze related action at a level encompassing multiple states, possibly in a region (Gruber, 2000; Hix & Høyland, 2011). A key distinction to supranational public policies is that they are non-legally binding. As such, they do not directly oblige states to comply with specified standards or create legal accountability. They could, however, be integrated into legal frameworks and become legally binding through relevant legislative processes (Gruber, 2000; Hix & Høyland, 2011). They can, for instance, provide the framework or basis for additional instruments such as trade agreements and public policies. State actors are the main actor group involved in initiating, negotiating, designing, and implementing the strategies and initiatives (Gruber, 2000). Strategies and initiatives can be combined with support mechanisms such as investments, financial support, capacity building, and technology transfer to achieve the specified goals and targets. Both state (e.g., governmental authorities) and nonstate actors (e.g., NGOs, specified corporate actors) can receive support and resources to implement the strategies and initiatives. Multiple examples exist at the EU level, such as the EU Farm to Fork Strategy for a fair, healthy and environmentally-friendly food system (Schebesta & Candel, 2020), the EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030, the EU Forest Strategy for 2030, and the European Green Deal. Other examples are the African Union's Agenda 2063, ASEAN'S ASCC (ASEAN Socio-Cultural Community) Blueprint 2025, the Belém Declaration, and at the Congo Basin regional level, the ban on the export of raw logs decided by member states of the Central African Economic and Monetary Community (which becomes legally binding once a member state adopts corresponding domestic legal measures) (Berning et al., 2023). A prominent example in the forest sector with a more external-action-oriented logic includes the FLEGT

Action Plan (which led to the legally binding FLEGT Regulation, FLEGT VPAs, EU Timber Regulation, and most recently, the EU Regulation on Deforestation-free products) (Cashore & Stone, 2012; Overdevest & Zeitlin, 2014; Zeitlin & Overdevest, 2021). A wildlife protection initiative includes the EU Action Plan Against Wildlife Trafficking (Berning et al., 2023).

Type II c: (Sub-)national level

Examples at the (sub-)national level include **strategies and initiatives** that are created to set or guide relevant policy and regulatory development at a national or subnational jurisdictional level or to catalyze related action (Kosti et al., 2019). They aim to provide a framework to achieve biodiversity and biomass-related targets. These strategies and initiatives remain non-legally binding (Kosti et al., 2019). However, they can lead to the state enacting legally binding instruments to operationalize them.

Mostly state actors are involved in this type, as governmental actors primarily design these strategies and initiatives. However, nonstate actors may also be part of the strategies' and initiatives' design, development, and implementation. The Brazilian National Climate Change Adaptation Plan of 2016, for instance, affirms that civil-society and private-sector representatives contributed to its drafting, and should be part of Goal 3.3's implementation working group on Ecosystem-Based Adaptation strategy. Both state (e.g., governmental authorities) and nonstate actors (e.g., NGOs, specified corporate actors) can receive support and resources to implement the strategies and initiatives.

Examples in commodity supply-side countries include the Brazil Ministry of Environment Ordinance 150/2016 on National Climate Change Adaptation Plan, the Cameroon National Strategy for Reducing Emissions from Deforestation and Forest Degradation, Sustainable Forest Management, Forest Conservation and Enhancing Carbon Stocks (Somorin et al., 2014), and the Gabon National Biodiversity Strategy and Action Plan (Berning et al., 2023).

Type III: State and nonstate actors, legally binding

Policies and governance mechanisms under type III jointly involve state and nonstate actors and are legally binding. We identified examples at the transnational level.

Type III b: Transnational level

Examples at the transnational level include transnational hybrid regulation and transnational hybrid free trade agreements. The overall goal of **transnational hybrid regulation** is to institutionalize transnational social, environmental, and economic standards regulated through a combination of public hard laws and voluntary private

governance mechanisms. These standards are frequently defined by import-dependent consumer countries and regions such as the EU, USA, and Australia, requesting compliance by supply-side countries (e.g., Brazil, Indonesia, Cameroon, Gabon) and/or transnational market actors (e.g., producers, manufacturers, traders, retailers) (e.g., Berning & Sotirov, 2023, Leipold et al., 2016; Partzsch, 2021; Sotirov et al., 2020). Transnational hybrid regulations are legally binding hard laws with command and control rules (e.g., prohibitions and due diligence requirements). Noncompliance can be enforced through sanctions (e.g., trade prohibitions) and penalties (e.g., financial penalties). At the same time, transnational hybrid regulations are frequently designed as a policy mix, combining hard laws with private regulation (e.g., acceptance of third-party verified schemes as compliance proof) and market incentives (e.g., exemptions under free trade agreements) (Berning & Sotirov, 2023; Dieguez & Sotirov, 2021; Sotirov et al., 2017). They are enacted by individual states or through a formally established body representing the states, whereby the states have ceded some of their national sovereignty to the body. Nonstate actors (e.g., NGOs, corporate actors) are frequently influential during the agenda-setting and regulatory design. Furthermore, states frequently rely on the watchdog function of (E)NGOs & CSOs (e.g., through substantiated concerns, information on noncompliance) during implementation, monitoring, and enforcement procedures (Abbott & Snidal; Berning & Sotirov, 2023; Hix & Høyland, 2011).

As such, hybrid regulation involves both state and nonstate actors, engaging in decision-making procedures and resource exchange (e.g., information, knowledge, finance). State agencies often remain in control of most regulatory tasks while delegating (or sharing with) some regulatory tasks to nonstate actors (e.g., NGOs and industry associations), legitimizing them as authority holders (Berning & Sotirov, 2023; Börzel & Risse, 2010; Kramarz & Park, 2019).

Key examples from the so-called timber legality regime include the EU Timber Regulation (EUTR)¹, the UK Timber and Timber Products Placing on the Market Regulation (UKTR), Australia's Illegal Logging Prohibition Act (ILPA), the Japanese Clean Wood Act (CWA), the Swiss Timber Trade Ordinance, and The South Korean Act on Sustainable Use of Timbers (Berning et al., 2022; Overdevest & Zeitlin, 2014; Zeitlin & Overdevest, 2021). Key examples from the newly emerging agricultural forest-risk commodity regime include the EU Regulation on Deforestation-free products (EUDR), UK due diligence provisions under the Environment Act 2021 (draft), and the US FOREST ACT of 2021 (draft) (Berning et al., 2022; Berning & Sotirov, 2023). Examples from the renewable energy sector include the EU's Renewable Energy Directives (RED) I and II (Partzsch, 2021; Moser & Leipold). Marine biomass-related initiatives include the EU Regulation to prevent, deter and eliminate illegal, unreported and unregulated fishing (IUU) (Berning et al., 2023).

¹ Which is repealed by the EU Regulation on deforestation-free products (EUDR)

Similar to transnational free trade agreements (see type I b), **transnational hybrid free trade agreements** aim to establish bilaterally or multilaterally agreed trade rules to facilitate trade and economic development. However, they have a stronger involvement of nonstate actors (e.g., (E)NGOs, CSOs) during the design (e.g., the definition of socio-environmental standards), implementation, and enforcement (e.g., watchdog function) procedures.

Key examples in the forest sector include the development-cooperation-based EU-partner country FLEGT Voluntary Partnership Agreements (VPAs) and UK-partner country FLEGT VPAs. These free trade agreements are market-building incentives under otherwise trade-restricting public policies (i.e., EUTR and UKTR) that are combined with development cooperation support commitments (e.g., financial, technical, capacity building support) (Berning & Sotirov, 2023; Overdevest & Zeitlin, 2014). Partner countries must set up national timber legality licensing and assurance systems (TLAS) to reap EU and UK market benefits (e.g., Article 13 "market incentives" under the EU-Indonesia FLEGT VPA). Effective VPA implementation requires tropical partner countries to agree on a national, multi-stakeholder definition of timber legality that is agreed upon by the government, private sector, and civil society. In return, the EU – also negotiating on behalf of the EU Member States – committed to supporting VPA countries with capacity building and technical assistance to implement TLAS systems. Furthermore, FLEGT-licensed timber and timber products had been granted a "green lane" market advantage under the EUTR, where FLEGT-licensed timber automatically fulfills the EUTR's due diligence requirements, facilitating its import to the EU market. Table 2 provides an overview of the EU-partner country FLEGT VPA negotiation and implementation stages. However, cooperation with the EU may change in the future context of the EUDR and newly emerging Forest Partnerships (see type II b and type III b).

Table 2: EU-partner country VPA overview.

EU-partner country FLEGT VPA implementation stage	Scope	Countries
Full FLEGT VPA implementation	VPA agreement signed and ratified, TLAS set up and operating. Issuing FLEGT licenses since 2016.	Indonesia
Partial FLEGT VPA implementation	VPA agreement signed and ratified. VPA published in the Official Journal of the EU. Development of TLAS.	Ghana, the Republic of the Congo, Cameroon, the Central African Republic, Liberia, Viet Nam
Partial FLEGT VPA implementation	Concluded negotiations.	Honduras, Guyana
FLEGT VPA negotiation	Embarked on formal bilateral negotiations.	Ivory Coast, Democratic Republic of the Congo, Gabon, Laos, Malaysia (put on hold), Thailand

Type IV: State and nonstate actors, non-legally binding

Like type III, policies and governance mechanisms under type IV jointly involve state and nonstate actors. However, they are non-legally binding. We identified examples at the international and transnational levels.

Type IV a: International level

The main goal of **public-private partnerships** is to establish a collaborative instrument of governance concerning collective goods and environmental, political, and social matters. Different societal actors voluntarily partner to pursue a common interest, deciding on shared responsibilities and roles. Public-private partnerships are non-legally binding partnerships between state and nonstate actors in society. A partnership is where two or more actors agree to partner to achieve a common goal and have common ownership of its process, with shared responsibilities, roles, and outcomes.

Such partnerships constitute a hybrid type of governance, in which nonstate actors co-govern along with state actors for the provision of collective goods and governance of environmental, political, and social matters, and thereby adopt governance functions that have formerly been the sole authority of sovereign states (Schäferhoff et al., 2009). Actors include states, civil society organizations (e.g., NGOs), corporate actors (e.g., transnational corporations), and others.

The example identified at the international level includes the International Union for the Conservation of Nature (IUCN). Its foundation was based on Fontainebleau constitutive act on the International Union for the Protection of Nature, signed in 1948 by 18 states. Since its foundation, its membership includes governmental (i.e., states and government agencies) and nongovernmental (i.e., national and international NGOs) members. From 2016 onwards, indigenous peoples organizations also became members. This is the most well-recognized instance of international collaboration between governments and nonstate actors. Several conservation and sustainable development activities are done through the IUCN, the most visible being the publication of "red lists" of threatened species (Chester & Moomaw, 2008).

Type IV b: Transnational level

Public-private partnership at the transnational level follows the same reasoning regarding the overarching goal, implementation, and actor participation as in the international examples. Its transnational nature refers to collaboration across states, but not necessarily with a global scope (Börzel & Risse, 2005; Schäferhoff et al., 2009).

Relevant examples at the transnational level include the UNDP Conscious Food Systems Alliance (CoFSA), the UN Global Compact, and specifically on forests: the

Bonn Challenge, the Collaborative Partnership on Forests (CPF), The Tropical Forest Alliance, New York Declaration on Forests, and Lowering Emissions by Accelerating Forest finance (LEAF) Coalition (Berning et al., 2023; Sotirov et al., 2022).

Type V: Nonstate actors, legally binding

Policies and governance mechanisms under type V mostly involve nonstate actors and are legally binding under private law. We identified examples at the transnational and (sub-)national levels.

Type V b: Transnational level

Private regulation enables private actors to hold other private actors accountable through private law. This includes NGO-, industry, and multi-stakeholder-led certification schemes and standards. Private actors (e.g., the company seeking certification) enter into an agreement with other private actors (e.g., the certifier) about specified standards that need to be met to be certified. The main goal of this regulation is to set private socio-ecological FERC production and chain of custody standards and to increase the market uptake of sustainably and legally produced goods. Private regulation is primarily driven by soft market (dis)incentives (e.g., profit and influence loss after consumer boycotts), peer pressure (e.g., downstream or upstream pressure to follow peers' sustainability standards), reputational damage (e.g., naming-and-shaming), and interests in avoiding regulatory interventions (e.g., hard laws) (Abbott & Snidal, 2021; Berning & Sotirov, 2023; Garrett et al., 2019; Kramarz & Park, 2019; Lambin & Thorlakson, 2018). Market actors voluntarily agree to be audited, and failures to adopt or comply with agreed standards can be sanctioned with certificate withdrawal. Noncompliance can also result in market sanctions, including reputational loss, profit loss, lower share prices, a firm's collapse, and supply chain exclusion, depending on the adopted sustainability instruments' stringency and reputational damage (Kramarz & Park, 2019; Rueda et al., 2017).

Voluntary transnational private FERC regulation emerged due to the difficulties for states to regulate global production processes and associated sustainability challenges during the global deregulation waves of the 1980s and 1990s (Abbott & Snidal, 2021; Kramarz & Park, 2019). Private regulations developed through normative (dis)approval of (un)sustainable business practices from NGOs, CSOs, consumers, retailers, employees, and shareholders, as well as through market (dis)incentives (e.g., business reputation, price premium, market access, boycotts) (Garrett et al., 2019; Kramarz & Park, 2019; Partzsch, 2020; Rueda et al., 2017).

Nonstate actors are the main actors involved in initiating, designing, implementing, and enforcing private regulation initiatives. The state's role is limited to catalyzing, coordinating, and supporting regulatory activities, particularly during the agenda-setting, negotiation, and enforcement stages (e.g., preferential status and financial support) (Abbott & Snidal, 2021). Furthermore, private standards are frequently based

on compliance with existing national social and environmental protection hard laws (Abbott & Snidal, 2021; Lambin & Thorlakson, 2018).

Examples at the transnational level include incentive-based sustainability and legality certification schemes in the forest and agricultural sectors. These include NGO-led certifications (e.g., Rainforest Alliance), industry-led certification schemes (e.g., PEFC, 4C certification), and multistakeholder-led certification schemes (e.g., FSC, ISCC, RSPO, RTRS).

Type V c: (Sub-)national level

Private regulation at the (sub-)national level follows the same reasoning regarding the overarching goal, implementation, and actor participation as in the transnational examples. Identified (sub-)national examples include sanction-based industry-oriented bans and moratoria in Brazil, namely the G4 cattle agreement and the Brazilian Soy Moratorium (Berning et al., 2023).

Type VI: Nonstate actors, non-legally binding

Similar to type V, policies and governance mechanisms under type VI mostly involve nonstate actors. However, they are non-legally binding under private law. We identified examples at the transnational and (sub-)national levels.

Type VI b: Transnational level

The main goals of **industry self-regulation** (e.g., corporate pledges, corporate social responsibility activities) are to meet consumer demand for socially and ecologically sustainable goods and business conduct and to avoid reputational damage and associated economic consequences. It is a way for nonstate actors to hold themselves accountable through soft (i.e., voluntary) initiatives. These include voluntary commitments, codes of conduct, corporate social responsibility initiatives, and corporate coalitions.

Nonstate actors are the main actors involved in initiating, designing, and implementing industry self-regulation initiatives. The state's role is limited to catalyzing, coordinating, and supporting activities. Furthermore, private self-regulation is frequently based on compliance with existing national social and environmental protection hard laws (Abbott & Snidal, 2021; Lambin & Thorlakson, 2018).

Examples at the transnational level include voluntary commitments (e.g., zero deforestation pledges from multinational companies such as Nestlé and Unilever), codes of conduct (e.g., responsible sourcing practices, transparency initiatives), Corporate Social Responsibility initiatives (e.g., financial and capacity-building

support to smallholders, such as Mondelez International's Cocoa Life initiative in Brazil), and corporate coalitions (e.g., Consumer Goods Forum Forest Positive Coalition, Soy Transparency Coalition, Retail Soy Group, Global Roundtable for Sustainable Beef (GRSB)) (Abbott & Snidal, 2021; Berning et al., 2023; Berning & Sotoriv, 2023; Garrett et al., 2019).

Type VI c: (Sub-)national level

Industry self-regulation at the (sub-)national level follows the same reasoning regarding goal, implementation, and actor participation as in the transnational examples. Identified (sub-)national examples also include voluntary commitments (e.g., Brazilian's biggest retailer group "Grupo Pão de Açúcar"'s zero deforestation pledge and signing of the Cerrado Manifesto), codes of conduct (e.g., responsible sourcing practices, transparency initiatives), and Corporate Social Responsibility initiatives (e.g., financial and capacity-building support to smallholders) (Berning et al., 2023).

CONCLUSION

This report mapped key public and private policies and governance mechanisms regulating legal and/or sustainable forest and ecosystem-risk biomass supply chains across demand and supply-side countries and regions. Our results reveal a complex regime of international, transnational, and (sub-)national public and private policies and governance mechanisms. The policies and mechanisms are either voluntary or legally binding and involve a diversity of state and nonstate actors. In terms of the participation of actors, they either rely on the main participation of state actors, nonstate actors, or both state and nonstate actors during the different phases of policy and governance design and implementation. Whether actor groups are more active in certain stages than others differ depending on the specific policy and governance mechanism. Further research can analyze the direct involvement of actors in the different types, policies, and mechanisms in the different stages of agenda-setting, design, adoption, implementation, monitoring, enforcement, and review processes more thoroughly.

Further research on the (in)coherence between the different policies and governance mechanisms is needed due to important theoretical knowledge gaps concerning the design of smart policy mixes. This could help highlight where policies and governance mechanisms are in alignment, and common objectives are reinforced, where there may be duplication of efforts and resources or opportunities to build capacity to meet multiple objectives, or where there may be gaps, trade-offs, and unintended consequences.

PROJECT OUTPUTS ACHIEVED & OUTLOOK

Building on this classification of six policy and governance types, following research outputs zoom in to map the designed and expected theories of change of a selection of key forest- and ecosystem-related policies and governance mechanisms regulating global biomass trade and biodiversity conservation.

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